

**ORGANIZATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DENTAL
CARE DURING THE PANDEMIC OF THE NEW CORONAVIRUS
INFECTION**

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Annotation: In 2020/1, the National Health Commission of China listed the novel coronavirus disease (covid-19) as a group B disease, including acute respiratory viral infections and highly pathogenic avian influenza [22]. But it recommended that all health workers use the prescribed protective equipment against group A infections, especially dangerous ones such as cholera. As usual, health workers are quickly caught in trouble due to national emergencies, often working tirelessly day and night. Dentists have a significantly higher risk of contracting covid-19 than workers, nurses, and general practitioners [8]. Therefore, it is very important to study the problem of covid-19 from the perspective of dental practice. Epidemiological and etiological problems of novel coronavirus infection: the emergence of a dentist in Wuhan, China, the spread of 2019 novel coronavirus disease (covid-19) has become a major public health problem not only for China but also for countries around the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared the covid-19 outbreak a public health emergency of international concern. The novel coronavirus was originally named 2019-ncov and officially known as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Recent studies have shown that, like sars-cov coronavirus and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), SARS-cov-2 is an infectious disease of animals, the main cause of which is the Chinese horseshoe bat (*Rhinolophus sinicus*) [5,19] and a lizard as an intermediate host-pathogen. most likely, intermediate servers [27]. Based on the results of genetic and epidemiological

studies, it was found that the covid-19 epidemic began with animal-to-human transmission of the virus, followed by stable human-to-human spread of the virus [5,7]. In addition to animal origin, the SARS-cov-2 acute protein fully interacts with human Ace2 receptors and helps transmit infections from human to human. The angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 receptor (ACE2) is the main receptor for the virus's Spike protein and detects pathogenic infections [9,30]. In addition to the respiratory system, the Ace2 receptor protein (more than 80% of the lung alveolar cells) is found in the main squamous epithelium of the nasal mucosa, oral cavity and nasopharynx, epithelial cells of the salivary glands, glandular cells of the intestine, sage cells of the colon and pancreas [17]. Currently, it is assumed that the mutual transmission occurs mainly by air droplets and exposure. [27] Moreover, there may be a risk of fecal-oral transmission, since researchers have identified SARS-CoV-2 in the feces of patients in China and the United States. [13] However, the question of whether SARS-CoV-2 is transmitted by aerosols or by vertical transmission (from mother to child) remains to be confirmed [6,34,41]. Although symptomatic covid-19 patients are the main source of infection, recent observations have shown that patients can be asymptomatic and latent and are carriers of SARS-CoV-2 [5,24]. This epidemiological feature of covid-19 makes it very difficult and opposes the timely identification and isolation of these patients, as this may lead to the accumulation of SARS-CoV-2 in society [27]. Moreover, breastfeeding patients have not been proven to be a possible source of infection. [24] As in other countries of the world, the issue of covid-19 is actively studied in the Kyrgyz Republic [1,2,3]. As of August 11, 2020, 19,936,547 people are infected worldwide. The daily increase in the number of infected people reaches 272.6 thousand. During the entire pandemic, 732,284 infected people died, and more than 12 million people recovered. The country most affected by SARS-CoV-2 is the United States (more than 4.88 million infected people). Brazil ranks second (more than 291 million), India (more than 196 million) in third place. Russia (871.8 thousand) in fourth

place, ahead of South Africa (538.1 thousand). Mexico, Peru, Chile, Colombia and Iran are also in the top ten. Most of the victims of the infection were registered in the United States - 163,156 people. Moreover, in the European countries most affected by the pandemic, a high mortality rate has been recorded. This figure exceeds 10% [33]. According to the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2010-2017), the mortality rate from COVID-19 (total mortality divided by cumulative cases) ranges from 0.39% to 4.05%, depending on the region of China and SARS (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome; 2020) and MERS (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome; over 10%), with seasonal influenza occurring at higher rates (0.01% to 0.17%) [14]. ... Current observations indicate that people of all ages are susceptible to this new contagion. However, people who are in close contact with symptomatic and asymptomatic COVID-19 patients (including medical staff and other patients in the hospital) are at higher risk of developing SARS-CoV-2. An analysis of 138 COVID-19 patients hospitalized in Wuhan during the early stages of the outbreak found that 57 (41%) hospitals were suspected of infection, 40 (29%) medical staff and 17 (12%) patients were hospitalized for other reasons. [31] As of February 14, 2020, a total of 1,716 medical workers in China have been infected with SARS-CoV-2, accounting for 3.8% of the national total, and six deaths have occurred in this group. Dentists hold a special position among medical professionals at risk for COVID-19 infection. On March 15, 2020, The New York Times published "Workers at High Risk for COVID-19 Infection." In these striking graphic images, it explains that dentists are workers at high risk of contracting COVID-19, far more so than nurses or general practitioners.[8] Dentists usually work closely with patients, so they are the first to make a diagnosis. Dentists may encounter patients with suspected or confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection and must not only provide care, but also make every effort to prevent the spread of nosocomial infection. Patients who cough, sneeze, or undergo dental treatment, including using high-speed ultrasonic devices, release secretions, saliva, or blood

into the environment. Dental instruments can become contaminated with various pathogens after use or affect a contaminated clinical environment. Infection can occur when sharp instruments puncture or when mucous membranes come into direct contact with contaminated hands. [14] Due to the peculiarities of dental procedures, where a large number of droplets and aerosols can appear, standard protective measures in daily clinical work are not effective enough to prevent the spread of COVID-19, especially when patients are unaware that they have an infection characterized by small size. Damage to the salivary glands and oral mucosa In new coronavirus infections, the ACE2 receptor is the main site of contact with SARS-CoV viral proteins [38]. Previous studies of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) have revealed infection of salivary gland epithelial cells with high ace2 expression [18]. ACE2 expression in human organs using GTEXport (<https://www.gtexportal.org/home/gene/ACE2#geneE>) is higher in small salivary glands than in the lungs (PTM in the pulmonary environment), suggesting that salivary glands may be a potential target of COVID-19. Furthermore, SARS-CoV RNA can be detected in saliva before lung damage occurs [32], which may explain the existence of asymptomatic sexually transmitted infections. In the case of SARS-CoV, salivary glands may be the main source of virus in saliva [18]. The level of positive results for COVID-19 in patients' saliva can reach 91.7%, and live virus can also be detected in saliva samples. [28] This suggests that COVID-19 transmitted in asymptomatic infections can be acquired from infected saliva. Researchers have shown the role of the oral mucosa in the development of COVID-19 infection [36,38]. There are at least 3 different ways in which COVID-19 may spread through saliva. First, COVID-19 originates in the lower and upper respiratory tract [39,40], entering the oral cavity along with droplets of fluid that are usually exchanged between these organs. On Monday, COVID-19 present in the blood can enter the oral cavity through a liquid resembling openwork formed from oral-specific secretions containing extracellular

matrix and whey proteins. [25] Finally, COVID-19 may enter the oral cavity in another way - affecting the large and small salivary glands, which secrete salivary particles through the salivary ducts. It has been shown that salivary gland epithelial cells can be infected with SARS-CoV immediately after infection in rhesus macaques, which may be the main source of this virus in saliva [18]. Carreraspresas M. et al. described lesions of the oral mucosa occurring in patients with positive test results or suspected covid-19 [4]. The lesions are characterized by painful sores and blisters. Between Tuesday and Monday, one patient was diagnosed with SARS-cov-2, the second patient is the husband of the woman with SARS-cov-2, and the third patient had fever, weakness, low blood pressure and loss of taste, but was not tested for COVID-19 because he did not have any serious symptoms. All lesions heal within 3-10 days. . A patient with a positive reaction to SARS-CoV-2, mentioned by Carreras-Presas et al., had pain in the tongue [4], which may be due to higher expression of the ACE2 receptor SARS-CoV-2 in the epithelial cells of the tongue, compared with buccal or gingival tissues [35]. Taking into account that anosmia and ageusia (olfactory and gustatory dysfunctions) have been confirmed as symptoms of COVID-19 caused by inflammation [16], it can be assumed that COVID-19 may include oral signs and symptoms, the study of which should be given special attention. Lesions of the oral mucosa can be the result of many other factors, such as stress due to the limitations of social life during the COVID-19 pandemic, lack of oral hygiene, mechanical pressure [10] or herpes simplex virus [4]. Topical antiseptic oral applications recommended to reduce viral load in the oral cavity, such as mouthwash solutions based on hydrogen peroxide [12], can also cause mouth ulcers [11]. A carefully collected medical history, well-conducted laboratory and instrumental studies will help to identify the cause of the lesion of the oral cavity. Since the oral mucosa may be the first area infected with SARSCoV-2, it can be assumed that lesions of the oral mucosa may be the first signs of COVID-19 if they are considered as signs of COVID-19. If studies confirm this

hypothesis, dental practitioners will be the first to identify patients with suspected SARS-CoV-2 and be able to send them for testing and appropriate treatment. Preventive measures during dental procedures in patients with COVID19. Inhalation of airborne particles and aerosols produced during dental procedures in patients with COVID-19 may be a high-risk procedure in which dentists are directly and closely exposed to this virus. Therefore, it is extremely important for dentists to improve preventive strategies to avoid COVID-19 infection by focusing on patient placement, hand hygiene, the use of all personal protective equipment (PPE) and caution when performing procedures related to aerosol formation. Hand hygiene is considered the most important measure to reduce the risk of transmission of microorganisms to patients [15]. SARS-CoV-2 can persist on the surface for several hours to several days, depending on the type of surface, temperature or humidity of the environment [34]. This reinforces the need for good hand hygiene and the importance of thorough disinfection of all surfaces in a dental clinic. To protect the skin and mucous membranes from infected blood or secretions, it is recommended to use personal protective equipment, including masks, gloves, bathrobes and safety glasses or a protective mask. Since respiratory droplets are the main route of transmission of SARS-CoV-2, particle respirators (for example, masks N-95, tested by the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health, or masks of the FFP2 standard, established by the European Union) are recommended for daily dental practice. An interesting article was recently published, written by researchers from Wuhan University School and Dental Hospital, which gave several recommendations for dentists and dental students on the management of patients with COVID-19 [21]. Dentists have been advised to take several personal protective measures and avoid or minimize operations that may result in droplets or aerosols; in addition, the use of salivary pumps with small or large volume can reduce the formation of droplets and aerosols. Given the severity of the COVID19 pandemic, it is important to provide clear and simple safety recommendations

against any risk of dental work. The fundamental concept is that the transmission of the virus occurs mainly through inhalation/ingestion / direct mucous contact with saliva droplets; It is also important to remember that the virus can survive on hands [21,23].

Conclusion: The scale and severity of the changes will be determined by the data from studies to identify optimal and safe methods of prevention, as well as organizational and methodological measures. Before sanctioning changes that will entail major financial and architectural changes in an existing dental office, it is necessary to conduct studies that will assess the availability for practicing dentists of organizational and methodological measures that can reduce/eliminate the risk of transmission of a new coronavirus infection.

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